

Sentinel-1 ARD from VHR DEM Technical Note

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EDAP+.REP.032

Issue: 1.1

29/03/2023

AMENDMENT RECORD SHEET

The Amendment Record Sheet below records the history and issue status of this document.

ISSUE	DATE	REASON
1.0	21/03/2023	Delivery to ESA and Telespazio
1.1	29/03/2023	Corrections of Amy Beaton (Telespazio)

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In order to set them as ready for analysis, RADAR data must be calibrated. This calibration can be processed considering a flat surface or taking into account the topography. This last processing, entitled Radiometric Terrain Correction (RTC), requires a Digital Elevation Model (DEM) in order to be applied. Generally, a Medium Resolution (MR) DEM is considered for this processing. In the latter years, several Very High Resolution (VHR) DEMs of cities, regions and countries were released publicly, allowing the usage of VHR DEMs for the RTC of RADAR data.

The goal of this document is to assess the impact of the DEM resolution on the quality of the Radiometric Terrain Correction (RTC) radar products, and therefore, its impact on the generation of Analysis Ready Data (ARD).

For this assessment, the RTC is applied to Sentinel-1 GRD products using Copernicus DEM GLO-30 (MR DEM). Over the four study areas considered, this RTC is also computed using a local VHR DEM. Two VHR DEMs are considered: RGEALTI (France) and ITA-TRE_DSM (Trentino, Italy).

Overall, this assessment shows that the VHR DEMs give better results than the MR DEMs for the Radiometric Terrain Correction. More homogeneous corrections are observed with VHR DEMs than with MR DEMs, which is particularly visible over steep areas.

Moreover, aggregated versions of the VHR DEMs show better RTC results than MR DEMs, up to 160 metres of resolution. Such a superiority witnesses that geomorphological elements are present in the VHR DEM even when lowering its spatial resolution. These geomorphological elements are not present or not correctly rendered in the MR DEM and prevent a reliable calculation of the local slope. However, the use of an aggregated VHR DEM is not advised, as an “aliasing effect” is visible on the terrain corrected scenes, starting at 80 metres of resolution.

1.1 References

The following is a list of reference documents with a direct bearing on the content of this proposal. Where referenced in the text, these are identified as [RD-n], where 'n' is the number in the list below:

1.1.1 Processing methods

- RD-1.** J.P. Rudant & al., 2019 *Téledétection radar: de l'image d'intensité initiale au choix du mode de calibration des coefficients de diffusion beta 0, sigma 0, gamma 0.* Revue Française de Photogrammétrie et de Téledétection, (219-220), 19-28.
<https://doi.org/10.52638/rfpt.2019.454>
- RD-2.** D. Small, 2011 *Flattening Gamma: Radiometric Terrain Correction for SAR Imagery,* IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing, vol. 49, no. 8, pp. 3081-3093, Aug. 2011
<https://doi.org/10.1109/TGRS.2011.2120616>
- RD-3.** ITI *Introduction au Traitement d'Image*
Cours S. Riazanoff, University Paris-Est
<http://www-igm.univ-mlv.fr/~riazano/enseignement/SR-ITI-COURS-02-09.pdf>
- RD-4.** TIG *Téledétection et Information Géographique*
Cours S. Riazanoff, University Paris-Est
<http://www-igm.univ-mlv.fr/~riazano/enseignement/SR-TIG-COURS-01-21.pdf>

1.1.2 Copernicus DEMs

- RD-5.** Product Handbook *Copernicus Digital Elevation Model Product Handbook version 4.0, 3 June 2022*
Airbus
https://spacedata.copernicus.eu/documents/20123/121239/GEO1988-CopernicusDEM-SPE-002_ProductHandbook_I4.0.pdf
- RD-6.** TD-GS-PS-0021 *TanDEM-X - Ground Segment - DEM Products Specification Document*
issue 3.1, 05.08.2016
DLR
https://elib.dlr.de/108014/1/TD-GS-PS-0021_DEM-Product-Specification_v3.1.pdf
- RD-7.** *WorldDEM™ Technical Product Specification - Digital Surface Model, Digital Terrain Model*
version 2.5, April 2019 - Airbus
https://www.intelligence-airbusds.com/automne/api/docs/v1.0/document/download/ZG9jdXRoZXF1ZS1kb2N1bWVudC01NTcyOQ==/ZG9jdXRoZXF1ZS1maWxILTU1NzI4/WorldDEM_TechnicalSpecifications_Version2.6-202012.pdf
- RD-8.** P. Rizzoli & al., 2017 *Generation and performance assessment of the global TanDEM-X digital elevation model*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2017.08.008>
- RD-9.** Validation report *Copernicus DEM Validation Report*
version 3.0, 9 November 2020 - Airbus
https://spacedata.copernicus.eu/documents/20123/121239/GEO1988-CopernicusDEM-RP-001_ValidationReport_I3.0.pdf
- RD-10.** K. Becek & al., 2016 *Evaluation of Vertical Accuracy of the WorldDEM™ Using the Runway Method*
Remote Sens. 2016, 8(11), 934;
<https://doi.org/10.3390/rs8110934>

1.1.3 ITA_TRE DEMs

- RD-11.** Dataset presentation *LiDAR datasets presentation*
Provincia Autonoma di Trento
<http://www.territorio.provincia.tn.it/portal/server.pt/communitary/lidar/847/lidar/23954>

1.1.4 RGE ALTI

- RD-12.** DC_RGEALTI_2-0 *RGE ALTI Version 2.0 Descriptif de contenu*
September 2018 – IGN
https://geoservices.ign.fr/sites/default/files/2021-07/DC_RGEALTI_2-0.pdf
- RD-13.** DL_RGEALTI_2-0 *RGE ALTI Version 2.0 Descriptif de livraison*
January 2017 – IGN
https://geoservices.ign.fr/sites/default/files/2021-07/DL_RGEALTI_2-0.pdf

RD-14. SE_RGEALTI

RGE ALTI Version 2.0 Suivi des évolutions
September 2018 – IGN
https://geoservices.ign.fr/sites/default/files/2021-07/SE_RGEALTI.pdf

1.1.5 VRS

RD-15. BZ&TN

Bolzano e Trento
Ufficio per il rilevamento Geodetico - Regione
Autonoma Trentino Alto Adige
[https://earth-
info.nga.mil/index.php?dir=wgs84&action=wgs84](https://earth-info.nga.mil/index.php?dir=wgs84&action=wgs84)

RD-16. EGM

Earth Gravitational Model
National Geospatial-Intelligence Agency
[https://earth-
info.nga.mil/index.php?dir=wgs84&action=wgs84](https://earth-info.nga.mil/index.php?dir=wgs84&action=wgs84)

1.1.6 Other studies

RD-17. HYP-084-Sentinel

Comparison of the Sentinel-1 calibrations σ^0 , γ^0 and β^0
[https://visioterra.fr/telechargement/P317_ESA_EDAP/HYP-084-Sentinels-E_S1_Comparison_Sigma0-
Gamma0-Beta0.pdf](https://visioterra.fr/telechargement/P317_ESA_EDAP/HYP-084-Sentinels-E_S1_Comparison_Sigma0-Gamma0-Beta0.pdf)

RD-18. HYP-097-Sentinel

Comparison of the γ^0_T and γ^0_E Sentinel-1 calibrations
[https://visioterra.fr/telechargement/P317_ESA_EDAP/HYP-097-Sentinels-
E_S1_Comparison_Gamma0_Ellipsoide_Gamma0_Local.pdf](https://visioterra.fr/telechargement/P317_ESA_EDAP/HYP-097-Sentinels-E_S1_Comparison_Gamma0_Ellipsoide_Gamma0_Local.pdf)

1.2 Glossary

The following acronyms and abbreviations have been used in this Report.

ARD	Analysis Ready Data
C-SAR	C-band Synthetic Aperture Radar
COP-DEM GLO-30	Copernicus Digital Elevation Model Global at 30 metres (1" arcsecond at equator)
CRS	Coordinate Reference System
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
DSM	Digital Surface Model
DTM	Digital Terrain Model
GRD	Ground Range Detected
GSD	Ground Sampling Distance
MR	Medium Resolution
RADAR	Radio Detection And Ranging
RGEALTI	<i>Référentiel à Grande Echelle Altimétrique</i>
RTC	Radiometric Terrain Correction
SAR	Synthetic-Aperture Radar
SRTM	Shuttle Radar Topography Mission
SRTMGL1	Shuttle Radar Topography Mission Global 1 arc second
VHR	Very High Resolution
VRS	Vertical Reference System

2. SENTINEL-1 CALIBRATIONS AND RADIOMETRIC TERRAIN CORRECTION

2.1 Scope

In order to retrieve homogenous scenes, Sentinel-1 data must be calibrated. This section aims to present different calibration methods and their impact on the Sentinel-1 scenes.

The first subsection (see section 2.2) aims to present the σ^{0E} , γ^{0E} and β^0 calibrations methods, which are processed considering a flat surface.

The second subsection (see section 2.3) presents the **Radiometric Terrain Correction (RTC)** (see RD-2). This process uses a DEM to correct the effects of topography on Sentinel-1 scenes. This correction is applied to the γ^{0E} (ellipsoid) calibration, which results in γ^{0T} (RTC).

The third subsection (see section 2.4) aims to present the calibration methods on three different study areas. For each study area, the σ^{0E} , γ^{0E} and β^0 calibrations (ellipsoid based) are compared against each other. Moreover, the influence of the RTC on the calibration is observed by comparing γ^{0E} (ellipsoid based) and γ^{0T} (RTC, DEM based).

The figures and comments of this section are extracted from previous studies RD-17 and RD-18. Please refer to these documents for further information.

2.2 Calibrations

This section presents the ellipsoid-based and DEM-based calibrations. Equations of these calibrations are extracted from RD-1. Please refer to this reference document for further details.

fig. 1 – Sentinel-1 C-SAR acquisition modes (see [ESA](#)).

The fig. 1 summarizes the different acquisition modes of Sentinel-1. The bottom right figure illustrates the geometry of acquisition of Sentinel-1, in which the three areas A_β , A_σ and A_γ are highlighted. These areas are respectively considered for the computation of the β^0 , σ^{0E} and γ^{0E} calibrations.

Hereafter are shown examples of the σ^0_E , γ^0_E and β^0 calibrations.

fig. 2 – Ingende Territory – Equations and VV, VH, VV colour composite of σ^0_E (VV = [12, -3] dB, VH = [-16, -12] dB).

fig. 3 – Ingende Territory – Equations and VV, VH, VV colour composite of γ^0_E (VV = [-12, 0] dB, VH = [-15, -11] dB).

fig. 4 – Ingende Territory – Equations and VV, VH, VV colour composite of β^0 (VV = [-9, -2] dB, VH = [-14, -10] dB).

One can see an “equalizing” effect on the γ^0_E , which is not observed on the two other calibrations. As a consequence, this calibration is considered for the Radiometric Terrain Correction (RTC) presented in the next section.

2.3 Radiometric Terrain Correction (RTC)

The Radiometric Terrain Correction (RTC) considers a DEM to further homogenise Sentinel-1 radar data. The following example shows γ^0_T (using RTC) and γ^0_E (no RTC).

fig. 5 – Ingende Territory - VV, VH, VV colour composites of γ^0_T and γ^0_E (fig. a and fig. b, VV = [-12, 0] dB, VH = [-15, -11] dB)

As seen in fig. 5, the difference between the two calibrations is primarily due to the topography. Please refer to RD-2 for further details about the RTC.

2.4 Case studies

In this section, the Sentinel-1 calibrations are applied on three different study areas, which are:

- **1. Ingende Territory**, Democratic Republic of the Congo,
- **2. Kahuzi-Biega National Park**, Democratic Republic of the Congo,
- **3. Tanganyika Lake**, on the borders between Democratic Republic of the Congo, Rwanda and Burundi.

Over each study area, the following comparisons are performed:

- **σ^0_E vs. γ^0_E vs. β^0 calibrations** – The three calibrations are individually applied to the same Sentinel-1 scene. As previously noted, these calibrations consider the ellipsoid as a reference surface. An image of the differences between γ^0_E and σ^0_E is computed.
- **γ^0_T vs. γ^0_E calibrations** – The two calibrations are individually applied to the same Sentinel-1 scene. As previously noted, the γ^0_E calibration considers the ellipsoid, whereas the γ^0_T calibration considers a DEM to perform a Radiometric Terrain Correction. In this case, the SRTMGL1 v003 DEM is used to perform this correction.

2.4.1 Case 1 – Ingende Territory

2.4.1.1 σ^0_E vs. γ^0_E vs. β^0 calibrations

fig. 6 – Ingende Territory - VV, VH, VV colour composites of σ^0_E (fig. a, VV = [12, -3] dB, VH = [-16, -12] dB), γ^0_E (fig. b, VV = [-12, 0] dB, VH = [-15, -11] dB) and β^0 (fig. c, VV = [-9, -2] dB, VH = [-14, -10] dB), VV difference ($\gamma^0 - \sigma^0$).

As seen in fig. 6, calibrations σ^0_E and β^0 are brighter in *near range* (East part of the image in descending orbit) than in *far range* (West part). On the opposite, the γ^0_E seems homogenous and does not present this phenomenon.

2.4.1.1 γ^0_T vs. γ^0_E calibrations

fig. 7 – Ingende Territory - VV, VH, VV colour composites of γ^0_T and γ^0_E (fig. a and fig. b, VV = [-12, 0] dB, VH = [-15,-11] dB VV difference (fig. c and fig. d, $\gamma^0_T - \gamma^0_E$).

In an area with low slopes such as Ingende, the fig. 7 shows that the γ^0_T calibration algorithm leads to a lowering of the backscattered signal from 0.1 dB to slightly more than 1 dB. The subfigures c and d show that the difference between the two calibrations is linked to the local variation of the topography.

2.4.2 Case 2 – Kahuzi-Biega National Park

2.4.2.1 σ^0_E vs. γ^0_E vs. β^0 calibrations

Because of the low variations of the slopes observed in the Ingende Territory (see case 1 in previous section 2.4.1), an area with a more important relief is chosen. This zone is the Kahuzi-Biega National Park, showing rifts and escarpments.

fig. 8 – Kahuzi-Biega National Park - VV, VH, VV colour composites of σ^0_E (fig. a, VV = [12, -3] dB, VH = [-16, -12] dB), γ^0_E (fig. b, VV = [-12, 0] dB, VH = [-15, -11] dB) and β^0 (fig. c, VV = [-9, -2] dB, VH = [-14, -10] dB), VV difference ($\gamma^0_E - \sigma^0_E$).

One may observe the same overall distribution of the brightness and contrast than seen in case 1 (Ingende Territory). Again, calibrations σ^0_E and β^0 are brighter in *near range* (East part of the image in descending orbit) than in *far range* (West part). The γ^0 calibration shows an « equalizing » effect over the tropical forest, even considering important slopes.

2.4.2.2 γ^0_T vs. γ^0_E calibrations

fig. 9 – Kahuzi-Biega National Park - VV, VH, VV colour composites of γ^0_T and γ^0_E (fig. a and fig. b, VV = [-12, 0] dB, VH = [-15, -11] dB VV difference (fig. c and fig. d, $\gamma^0_T - \gamma^0_E$).

In this zone, the terrain correction seems to result in important negative and positive differences (<-2 dB or > +2 dB) over the landforms, with a low loss of signal backscattering over the plains (approximately -0.1 dB). The positive differences seem to be located on the opposite side of the one exposed to the radar signal.

Less artifacts seem to be linked to the slopes in γ^0_T than in the γ^0_E image.

2.4.3 Case 3 – Tanganyika Lake

2.4.3.1 σ^0_E vs. γ^0_E vs. β^0 calibrations

fig. 10 – Tanganyika Lake - VV, VH, VV colour composites of σ^0_E (fig. a, VV = [12, -3] dB, VH = [-16, -12] dB), γ^0_E (fig. b, VV = [-12, 0] dB, VH = [-15, -11] dB) and β^0 (fig. c, VV = [-9, -2] dB, VH = [-14, -10] dB), VV difference ($\gamma^0_E - \sigma^0_E$).

In fig. 10, two adjacent segments are processed, each one including three Sentinel-1 IW scenes. In this view of the East of DRC, the land use differs from one side to another of the Tanganyika Lake. The West part is mountainous and covered by forests (especially in its North part) The plains located at the East of the Lake lesser reflect the radar signal and are particularly dark.

The limit between two segments is particularly visible with the σ^0_E and β^0 calibrations, whereas this limit is almost indiscernible with the γ^0_E calibration.

2.4.3.2 γ^0_T vs. γ^0_E calibrations

fig. 11 – Tanganyika Lake - VV, VH, VV colour composites of γ^0_T and γ^0_E (fig. a and fig. b, VV = [-12, -2] dB, VH = [-16, -12] dB VV difference (fig. c and fig. d, $\gamma^0_T - \gamma^0_E$).

In this mountainous region, differences are even more important than the ones observed in the Kahuzi-Biega National Park (see previous section 2.4.2): negative differences are located on the sides exposed to the satellite, whereas the positive differences are on the opposite side. One can see important differences over the crests (> 2 dB). The scene seems more homogenous in the case of γ^0_T than in the case of the ellipsoid.

3. IMPACT OF THE DEM RESOLUTION ON THE QUALITY OF THE RADIOMETRIC TERRAIN CORRECTION

3.1 Scope

In this section, Sentinel-1 data is calibrated considering different DEMs for the Radiometric Terrain Correction. These DEMs may be Medium Resolution or Very High Resolution. The goal of this assessment is to find the impact of the resolution of DEMs on the quality of the Radiometric Terrain Correction (see RD-2).

3.1.1 Study areas

In this assessment, four study areas have been considered, as shown in the following figures.

fig. 12 – Overview of the study areas.

3.1.2 DEMs

3.1.2.1 Medium Resolution DEMs

The following table summarizes the characteristics of the Medium Resolution DEM used in this study.

Name	Copernicus DEM GLO-30
Overview	
Version	2021_1_DGED
Type	DSM
GSD	1" arcsecond (≈ 30 m along equator)
Spatial Extent	Global
CRS	EPSG:4326
VRS	EGM2008

fig. 13 – Characteristics of Copernicus DEM GLO-30.

3.1.2.2 Very High Resolution DEMs

The following table summarizes the characteristics of the Very High Resolution DEMs used in this study.

	ITA-TRE_DSM_1-2_2009	RGEALTI_v2.0
Overview		
Version	2009	2.0
Type	DSM (ITA-TRE_DSM) / DTM (ITA-TRE_DTM)	DTM
GSD	1-2 metres (depending on tile)	1 metre
Spatial Extent	Autonomous Province of Trento, Italy	France (includes overseas departments)
CRS	ETRS89 / local UTM	RGF93 v1 / Lambert-93 (Metropolitan France)
VRS	BZ&TN geoid	IGN1969 geoid

fig. 14 – Characteristics of the VHR DEMs.

3.2 Methods

3.2.1 Calibrations and RTC

The calibrations and RTC are introduced in the previous section 2. Please refer to this section for further details.

3.2.2 Multi-level standard grid

In this study, DEMs and Sentinel-1 products are organized on a multi-level standard grid. This grid allows the superimposition of raster data, and thus, the comparison at any scale.

fig. 15 – Illustration of the quadtree organization and levels.

As seen in fig. 15, this grid is composed of multiple levels. In the following study, the RTC of MR DEMs and VHR DEMs will be compared at level 12 (19.11 m of resolution), which is slightly higher than the Copernicus DEM GLO-30 resolution (1" arcsecond, 30 metres at equator). Then, the RTC is performed by aggregating the VHR DEM at different levels, starting from level 13 (9.55 m) down to level 9 (152.87 m).

For an easier understanding, approximate resolutions are given hereafter instead of the actual resolutions (see table of fig. 15).

3.3 Results

3.3.1 Massif de La Dôle (Jura), France

The following figure illustrates the study area of the Massif de la Dôle, in France.

fig. 16 – RGEALTI over the Massif de La Dôle, France – Overview of the three study areas.

As seen in fig. 16, this area is divided into three sub-areas, which are individually analysed in the next sub-sections.

3.3.1.1 Area 1

fig. 17 – GLO-30 and RGEALTI over the Massif de La Dôle, France – Overview of area 1.

From the overview of fig. 17, one can observe the following:

- **Heights** – As expected, at 20 metres of resolution, which is the closest to GLO-30 in the quadtree architecture, RGEALTI shows sharper details than GLO-30.
- **Sources** – GLO-30 heights are mainly from TanDEM-X data, with some edited pixels and “SRTM30” data. As suggested by its name, the “SRTM30” has the same resolution of 30 m at equator than the GLO-30 data. The RGEALTI data only shows LiDAR elevations with no additional processing.
- **Vertical curvatures** – One may see the characteristic lines of the terrain in both DEMs. Sharper and stronger curvature lines are observed over RGEALTI than over GLO-30.
- **RTC (γ^0_T)** – One may see dark areas using GLO-30 for the RTC. At the same resolution of 20 m, such dark areas are not seen using RGEALTI, which shows a much more homogeneous surface.

Hereafter is shown the RTC using RGEALTI at different resolutions.

fig. 18 – RGEALTI over the Massif de La Dôle, France – RTC using RGEALTI at different resolution on area 1.

Based on the RTCs at different resolutions seen in fig. 18, one can observe the following:

- **Aliasing effect when lowering the resolution** - Lowering the resolution mainly results in “aliasing effects”. Over this area, these effects are mainly seen at 160 m of resolution, where square shapes can be observed over the Sentinel-1 scene.
- **Better results than GLO-30, even at lower resolutions** – One can see that Sentinel-1 scenes are better corrected using RGEALTI, even at low resolutions of 80 m or 160 m, than using GLO-30 at 20 metres of resolution.

3.3.1.2 Area 2

- Edited (except filled pixels)
- Not edited / not filled
- ASTER
- SRTM90
- SRTM30
- GMTED2010
- SRTM30plus
- TerraSAR-X Radargrammetric DEM
- AW3D30
- Norway DEM

- Pas de données
- Raccord
- Numérisation manuelle ou vectorisation
- Restitution photogrammétrique PVA
- LIDAR mixte Bathy SHOM
- LIDAR Bathy SHOM
- SMF SHOM
- LIDAR Topo IGN
- LIDAR Topo IGN interpolation
- Translation en Z à partir du MNE LIDAR Topo IGN
- LIDAR Topo IGN sans corrections interactives
- Lidar Topo IGN Point Fictif
- Origines multiples produit Litto3D®
- LIDAR Topo externe
- LIDAR Topo externe interpolation
- LIDAR Topo externe sans corrections interactives
- LIDAR Topo externe Point Fictif
- Corrélation automatique PVA HR 30 cm >= pixel => 20 cm
- Corrélation automatique PVA HR 20 cm > pixel => 10
- Corrélation automatique PVA HR pixel < 10 cm
- Corrélation automatique acquisition externe PVA HR 30 cm
- Corrélation automatique PVA non HR pixel > 30 cm
- Données interpolées à partir de données existantes
- MNT grille externe issu d'acquisition LIDAR
- MNT grille externe issu de corrélation automatique
- LIDAR Topo IGN en forêt
- LIDAR Topo IGN en forêt interpolation
- LIDAR Topo IGN en forêt sans corrections interactives
- LIDAR Topo IGN en forêt Point Fictif

fig. 19 – GLO-30 and RGEALTI over the Massif de La Dôle, France – Overview of area 2.

From the overview of fig. 19, one can observe the following:

- **Heights** – As expected, at 20 metres of resolution, which is the closest to GLO-30 in the quadtree architecture, RGEALTI shows sharper details than GLO-30.
- **Sources** – GLO-30 heights are mainly from TanDEM-X data, with some edited pixels and “SRTM30” data. Again, the “SRTM30” has the same resolution of 30 m at equator than the GLO-30 data. The RGEALTI data mostly shows external LiDAR elevations, with some IGN LiDAR data on the North-West and a merge boundary.
- **Vertical curvatures** – One may see the characteristic lines of the terrain in both DEMs. Sharper and stronger curvature lines are observed over RGEALTI than over GLO-30.
- **RTC (γ^0_T)** – One may see dark areas using GLO-30 for the RTC. At the same resolution of 20 m, such dark areas are not seen using RGEALTI, which shows a much more homogeneous surface.

Hereafter is shown the RTC using RGEALTI at different resolutions.

fig. 20 – RGEALTI over the Massif de La Dôle, France – RTC using RGEALTI at different resolution on area 2.

Based on the RTCs at different resolutions seen in fig. 20, one can observe the following:

- **Aliasing effect when lowering the resolution** - Lowering the resolution mainly results in “aliasing effects”. Over this area, these effects are mainly seen at 160 m of resolution, where square shapes can be observed over the Sentinel-1 scene.
- **Better results than GLO-30, even at lower resolutions** – One can see that Sentinel-1 scenes are better corrected using RGEALTI, even at low resolutions of 80 m or 160 m, than using GLO-30 at 20 metres of resolution.

3.3.1.1 Area 3

fig. 21 – GLO-30 and RGEALTI over the Massif de La Dôle, France – Overview of area 3.

From the overview of fig. 21, one can observe the following:

- **Heights** – As expected, at 20 metres of resolution, which is the closest to GLO-30 in the quadtree architecture, RGEALTI shows sharper details than GLO-30.
- **Sources** – GLO-30 heights are mainly from TanDEM-X data, with some edited pixels and “SRTM30” data over the mountain crest. Again, the “SRTM30” has the same resolution of 30 m at equator than the GLO-30 data. The RGEALTI data only shows external LiDAR elevations.
- **Vertical curvatures** – One may see the characteristic lines of the terrain in both DEMs. Sharper and stronger curvature lines are observed over RGEALTI than over GLO-30.
- **RTC (γ^0_T)** – One may see dark areas using GLO-30 for the RTC, especially on the North-West of the study area. At the same resolution of 20 m, such dark areas are not seen using RGEALTI, which shows a much more homogeneous surface.

Hereafter is shown the RTC using RGEALTI at different resolutions.

fig. 22 – RGEALTI over the Massif de La Dôle, France – RTC using RGEALTI at different resolution on area 3.

Based on the RTCs at different resolutions seen in fig. 22, one can observe the following:

- **Aliasing effect when lowering the resolution** - Lowering the resolution mainly results in “aliasing effects”. Over this area, these effects are mainly seen at 160 m of resolution, over the mountain crest.
- **Better results than GLO-30, even at lower resolutions** – One can see that Sentinel-1 scenes are better corrected using RGEALTI, even at low resolutions of 80 m or 160 m, than using GLO-30 at 20 metres of resolution.

3.3.2 Notre-Dame-du-Pré, France

The following figure illustrates the study area of Notre-Dame-du-Pré, in France.

fig. 23 – RGEALTI over the Notre-Dame-du-Pré, France – Overview of the two study areas.

As seen in fig. 23, this area is divided into two sub-areas, which are individually analysed in the next sub-sections.

3.3.2.1 Area 1

- Edited (except filled pixels)
- Not edited / not filled
- ASTER
- SRTM90
- SRTM30
- GMTED2010
- SRTM30plus
- TerraSAR-X Radargrammetric DEM
- AW3D30
- Norway DEM

- Pas de données
- Raccord
- Numérisation manuelle ou vectorisation
- Restitution photogrammétrique PVA
- LIDAR mixte Bathy SHOM
- LIDAR Bathy SHOM
- SMF SHOM
- LIDAR Topo IGN
- LIDAR Topo IGN interpolation
- Translation en Z à partir du MNE LIDAR Topo IGN
- LIDAR Topo IGN sans corrections interactives
- Lidar Topo IGN Point Fictif
- Origines multiples produit Litto3D®
- LIDAR Topo externe
- LIDAR Topo externe interpolation
- LIDAR Topo externe sans corrections interactives
- LIDAR Topo externe Point Fictif
- Corrélation automatique PVA HR 30 cm >= pixel => 20 cm
- Corrélation automatique PVA HR 20 cm > pixel => 10
- Corrélation automatique PVA HR pixel < 10 cm
- Corrélation automatique acquisition externe PVA HR 30 cm
- Corrélation automatique PVA non HR pixel > 30 cm
- Données interpolées à partir de données existantes
- MNT grille externe issu d'acquisition LIDAR
- MNT grille externe issu de corrélation automatique
- LIDAR Topo IGN en forêt
- LIDAR Topo IGN en forêt interpolation
- LIDAR Topo IGN en forêt sans corrections interactives
- LIDAR Topo IGN en forêt Point Fictif

fig. 24 – GLO-30 and RGEALTI over Notre-Dame-du-Pré, France – Overview of area 1.

From the overview of fig. 24, one can observe the following:

- **Heights** – As expected, at 20 metres of resolution, which is the closest to GLO-30 in the quadtree architecture, RGEALTI shows sharper details than GLO-30.
- **Sources** – GLO-30 heights are mainly from TanDEM-X data, with some edited pixels and “SRTM30” data. Again, the “SRTM30” has the same resolution of 30 m at equator than the GLO-30 data. The RGEALTI data shows both IGN LiDAR and external LiDAR data.
- **Vertical curvatures** – One may see the characteristic lines of the terrain in both DEMs. Sharper and stronger curvature lines are observed over RGEALTI than over GLO-30.
- **RTC (γ^0_{τ})** – One may see dark areas using GLO-30 for the RTC. At the same resolution of 20 m, such dark areas are not seen using RGEALTI, which shows a much more homogeneous surface.

Hereafter is shown the RTC using RGEALTI at different resolutions.

fig. 25 – RGEALTI over Notre-Dame-du-Pré, France – RTC using RGEALTI at different resolution on area 1.

Based on the RTCs at different resolutions seen in fig. 25, one can observe the following:

- **Aliasing effect when lowering the resolution** - Lowering the resolution mainly results in “aliasing effects”. Over this area, these effects are mainly seen at 160 m of resolution, where square shapes can be observed over the Sentinel-1 scene.
- **Better results than GLO-30, even at lower resolutions** – One can see that Sentinel-1 scenes are better corrected using RGEALTI, even at low resolutions of 80 m, than using GLO-30 at 20 m of resolution. Comparable results are obtained between RGEALTI at 160 m and GLO-30 at 20 m.

3.3.2.1 Area 2

fig. 26 – GLO-30 and RGEALTI over Notre-Dame-du-Pré, France – Overview of area 2.

From the overview of fig. 26, one can observe the following:

- **Heights** – As expected, at 20 metres of resolution, which is the closest to GLO-30 in the quadtree architecture, RGEALTI shows sharper details than GLO-30.
- **Sources** – GLO-30 heights are mainly from TanDEM-X data, with some edited pixels of “SRTM30” data and a few “ASTER”. Both DEMs have the same resolution of 30 m at equator than the GLO-30 data. The RGEALTI data mostly shows LiDAR data, with some photogrammetry from aerial photography.
- **Vertical curvatures** – One may see the characteristic lines of the terrain in both DEMs. Sharper and stronger curvature lines are observed over RGEALTI than over GLO-30.
- **RTC (γ^0_T)** – One may see dark areas using GLO-30 for the RTC. At the same resolution of 20 m, such dark areas are not seen using RGEALTI, which shows a much more homogeneous surface.

Hereafter is shown the RTC using RGEALTI at different resolutions.

fig. 27 – RGEALTI over Notre-Dame-du-Pré, France – RTC using RGEALTI at different resolution on area 2.

Based on the RTCs at different resolutions seen in fig. 27, one can observe the following:

- **Aliasing effect when lowering the resolution** - Lowering the resolution mainly results in “aliasing effects”. Over this area, these effects are mainly seen at 160 m of resolution, where square shapes can be observed over the Sentinel-1 scene.
- **Better results than GLO-30, even at lower resolutions** – One can see that Sentinel-1 scenes are better corrected using RGEALTI, even at low resolutions of 80 m, than using GLO-30 at 20 metres of resolution. Comparable results are obtained between RGEALTI at 160 m and GLO-30 at 20 m.

3.3.3 La Réunion, France

The following figure illustrates the study area of la Réunion, an overseas department of France.

fig. 28 – RGEALTI over the La Réunion, France – Overview of the three study areas.

As seen in fig. 28, this area is divided into three sub-areas, which are individually analysed in the next sub-sections.

3.3.3.1 Area 1

- Edited (except filled pixels)
- Not edited / not filled
- ASTER
- SRTM90
- SRTM30
- GMTED2010
- SRTM30plus
- TerraSAR-X Radargrammetric DEM
- AW3D30
- Norway DEM

- Pas de données
- Raccord
- Numérisation manuelle ou vectorisation
- Restitution photogrammétrique PVA
- LIDAR mixte Bathy SHOM
- LIDAR Bathy SHOM
- SMF SHOM
- LIDAR Topo IGN
- LIDAR Topo IGN interpolation
- Translation en Z à partir du MNE LIDAR Topo IGN
- LIDAR Topo IGN sans corrections interactives
- Lidar Topo IGN Point Fictif
- Origines multiples produit Litto3D®
- LIDAR Topo externe
- LIDAR Topo externe interpolation
- LIDAR Topo externe sans corrections interactives
- LIDAR Topo externe Point Fictif
- Corrélation automatique PVA HR 30 cm >= pixel => 20 cm
- Corrélation automatique PVA HR 20 cm > pixel => 10
- Corrélation automatique PVA HR pixel < 10 cm
- Corrélation automatique acquisition externe PVA HR 30 cm
- Corrélation automatique PVA non HR pixel > 30 cm
- Données interpolées à partir de données existantes
- MNT grille externe issu d'acquisition LIDAR
- MNT grille externe issu de corrélation automatique
- LIDAR Topo IGN en forêt
- LIDAR Topo IGN en forêt interpolation
- LIDAR Topo IGN en forêt sans corrections interactives
- LIDAR Topo IGN en forêt Point Fictif

fig. 29 – GLO-30 and RGEALTI over La Réunion, France – Overview of area 1.

From the overview of fig. 29, one can observe the following:

- **Heights** – As expected, at 20 metres of resolution, which is the closest to GLO-30 in the quadtree architecture, RGEALTI shows sharper details than GLO-30.
- **Sources** – GLO-30 heights are extracted from “ASTER and “SRTM30” data. Both DEMs have the same resolution of 30 m at equator than the GLO-30 data. The RGEALTI data mostly shows LiDAR data, with a few pixels interpolated.
- **Vertical curvatures** – One may see the characteristic lines of the terrain in both DEMs. Sharper and stronger curvature lines are observed over RGEALTI than over GLO-30.
- **RTC (γ^0_T)** – One may see dark areas using GLO-30 for the RTC. At the same resolution of 20 m, a much more homogeneous surface is obtained using RGEALTI than GLO-30.

Hereafter is shown the RTC using RGEALTI at different resolutions.

fig. 30 – RGEALTI over La Réunion, France – RTC using RGEALTI at different resolution on area 1.

Based on the RTCs at different resolutions seen in fig. 30, one can observe the following:

- **Aliasing effect when lowering the resolution** - Lowering the resolution mainly results in “aliasing effects”. Over this area, these effects are mainly seen at 80 m and 160 m of resolution, where square shapes can be observed over the Sentinel-1 scene.
- **Better results than GLO-30, even at lower resolutions** – One can see that Sentinel-1 scenes are better corrected using RGEALTI, even at a lower resolution of 40 m, than using GLO-30 at 20 metres of resolution.

3.3.3.1 Area 2

fig. 31 – GLO-30 and RGEALTI over La Réunion, France – Overview of area 2.

From the overview of fig. 31, one can observe the following:

- **Heights** – As expected, at 20 metres of resolution, which is the closest to GLO-30 in the quadtree architecture, RGEALTI shows sharper details than GLO-30.
- **Sources** – GLO-30 heights are extracted from “ASTER and “SRTM30” data, with a line of edited pixels. Both “ASTER” and “SRTM30” data sources have the same resolution of 30 m at equator than the GLO-30 data. The RGEALTI mostly shows LiDAR data, which have been translated vertically from the LiDAR Topo IGN DEM.
- **Vertical curvatures** – One may see the characteristic lines of the terrain in both DEMs. Sharper and stronger curvature lines are observed over RGEALTI than over GLO-30.
- **RTC (γ^0_T)** – One may see dark areas using GLO-30 for the RTC. At the same resolution of 20 m, almost no dark areas are seen using RGEALTI.

Hereafter is shown the RTC using RGEALTI at different resolutions.

fig. 32 – RGEALTI over La Réunion, France – RTC using RGEALTI at different resolution on area 2.

Based on the RTCs at different resolutions seen in fig. 32, one can observe the following:

- **Aliasing effect when lowering the resolution** - Lowering the resolution mainly results in “aliasing effects”. Over this area, these effects are mainly seen at 160 m of resolution, where square shapes can be observed over the Sentinel-1 scene.
- **Better results than GLO-30, even at lower resolutions** – One can see that Sentinel-1 scenes are better corrected using RGEALTI, even at low resolutions of 40 m or 80 m, than using GLO-30 at 20 metres of resolution.

3.3.3.1 Area 3

- Edited (except filled pixels)
- Not edited / not filled
- ASTER
- SRTM90
- SRTM30
- GMTED2010
- SRTM30plus
- TerraSAR-X Radargrammetric DEM
- AW3D30
- Norway DEM

- Pas de données
- Raccord
- Numérisation manuelle ou vectorisation
- Restitution photogrammétrique PVA
- LIDAR mixte Bathy SHOM
- LIDAR Bathy SHOM
- SMF SHOM
- LIDAR Topo IGN
- LIDAR Topo IGN interpolation
- Translation en Z à partir du MNE LIDAR Topo IGN
- LIDAR Topo IGN sans corrections interactives
- Lidar Topo IGN Point Fictif
- Origines multiples produit Litto3D®
- LIDAR Topo externe
- LIDAR Topo externe interpolation
- LIDAR Topo externe sans corrections interactives
- LIDAR Topo externe Point Fictif
- Corrélation automatique PVA HR 30 cm >= pixel => 20 cm
- Corrélation automatique PVA HR 20 cm > pixel => 10
- Corrélation automatique PVA HR pixel < 10 cm
- Corrélation automatique acquisition externe PVA HR 30 cm
- Corrélation automatique PVA non HR pixel > 30 cm
- Données interpolées à partir de données existantes
- MNT grille externe issu d'acquisition LIDAR
- MNT grille externe issu de corrélation LIDAR
- LIDAR Topo IGN en forêt
- LIDAR Topo IGN en forêt interpolation
- LIDAR Topo IGN en forêt sans corrections interactives
- LIDAR Topo IGN en forêt Point Fictif

fig. 33 – GLO-30 and RGEALTI over La Réunion, France – Overview of area 3.

From the overview of fig. 33, one can observe the following:

- **Heights** – As expected, at 20 metres of resolution, which is the closest to GLO-30 in the quadtree architecture, RGEALTI shows sharper details than GLO-30.
- **Sources** – GLO-30 heights are extracted from “ASTER and “SRTM30” data, with some TanDEM-X and edited pixels. Both “ASTER” and “SRTM30” data sources have the same resolution of 30 m at equator than the TanDEM-X data. The RGEALTI mostly shows LiDAR data, which have been translated vertically from the LiDAR Topo IGN DEM.
- **Vertical curvatures** – One may see the characteristic lines of the terrain in both DEMs. Sharper and stronger curvature lines are observed over RGEALTI than over GLO-30.
- **RTC (γ^0_T)** – One may see dark areas using GLO-30 for the RTC. At the same resolution of 20 m, fewer dark areas are seen using RGEALTI.

Hereafter is shown the RTC using RGEALTI at different resolutions.

fig. 34 – RGEALTI over La Réunion, France – RTC using RGEALTI at different resolution on area 3.

Based on the RTCs at different resolutions seen in fig. 34, one can observe the following:

- **Aliasing effect when lowering the resolution** - Lowering the resolution mainly results in “aliasing effects”. Over this area, these effects are mainly seen at 80 m and 160 m of resolution, where square shapes can be observed over the Sentinel-1 scene.
- **Better results than GLO-30, even at lower resolutions** – One can see that Sentinel-1 scenes are better corrected using RGEALTI, even at a lower resolution of 80 m, than using GLO-30 at 20 metres of resolution.

3.3.4 La Becca, Trentino, Italy

The following figure illustrates the study area of La Becca, in Trentino, Italy.

fig. 35 – RGEALTI over the Notre-Dame-du-Pré, France – Overview of the two study areas.

As seen in fig. 35, this area is divided into two sub-areas, which are individually analysed in the next sub-sections.

3.3.4.1 Area 1

fig. 36 – GLO-30 and ITA-TRE_DSM over La Becca, Trentino, Italy – Overview of area 1.

From the overview of fig. 36, one can observe the following:

- **Heights** – As expected, at 20 metres of resolution, which is the closest to GLO-30 in the quadtree architecture, ITA-TRE_DSM shows sharper details than GLO-30.
- **Sources** – GLO-30 heights mainly come from TanDEM-X, “ASTER” and “SRTM30”. All these data sources have the same resolution of 30 m at equator than the GLO-30 data. No source mask is available for ITA-TRE_DSM.
- **Vertical curvatures** – One may see the characteristic lines of the terrain in both DEMs. Sharper and stronger curvature lines are observed over ITA-TRE_DSM than over GLO-30.
- **RTC (γ^0_T)** – One may see dark areas using GLO-30 for the RTC. At the same resolution of 20 m, such dark areas are not seen using ITA-TRE_DSM, which shows a much more homogeneous surface.

Hereafter is shown the RTC using ITA-TRE_DSM at different resolutions.

fig. 37 – GLO-30 and ITA-TRE_DSM over La Becca, Trentino, Italy – RTC using ITA-TRE_DSM at different resolution on area 1.

Based on the RTCs at different resolutions seen in fig. 37, one can observe the following:

- **Aliasing effect when lowering the resolution** - Lowering the resolution mainly results in “aliasing effects”. Over this area, these effects are mainly seen at 160 m of resolution, where square shapes can be observed over the Sentinel-1 scene.
- **Better results than GLO-30, even at lower resolutions** – One can see that Sentinel-1 scenes are better corrected using ITA-TRE_DSM, even at a lower resolution of 80 m or 160 m, than using GLO-30 at 20 metres of resolution.

3.3.4.2 Area 2

fig. 38 – GLO-30 and ITA-TRE_DSM over La Becca, Trentino, Italy – Overview of area 1.

From the overview of fig. 38, one can observe the following:

- **Heights** – As expected, at 20 metres of resolution, which is the closest to GLO-30 in the quadtree architecture, ITA-TRE_DSM shows sharper details than GLO-30.
- **Sources** – GLO-30 heights mainly come from TanDEM-X, “ASTER”, “SRTM30”, “SRTM30plus” and some pixels from “SRTM90”. Excluding the few pixels of “SRTM90”, all of these data sources have the same resolution of 30 m at equator than the GLO-30 data. No source mask is available for ITA-TRE_DSM.
- **Vertical curvatures** – One may see the characteristic lines of the terrain in both DEMs. Sharper and stronger curvature lines are observed over ITA-TRE_DSM than over GLO-30.
- **RTC (γ^0_T)** – One may see dark areas using GLO-30 for the RTC. At the same resolution of 20 m, such dark areas are not seen using ITA-TRE_DSM, which shows a much more homogeneous surface.

Hereafter is shown the RTC using ITA-TRE_DSM at different resolutions.

fig. 39 – GLO-30 and ITA-TRE_DSM over La Becca, Trentino, Italy – RTC using ITA-TRE_DSM at different resolution on area 1.

Based on the RTCs at different resolutions seen in fig. 39, one can observe the following:

- **Aliasing effect when lowering the resolution** - Lowering the resolution mainly results in “aliasing effects”. Over this area, these effects are mainly seen at 160 m of resolution, where square shapes can be observed over the Sentinel-1 scene.
- **Better results than GLO-30, even at lower resolutions** – One can see that Sentinel-1 scenes are better corrected using ITA-TRE_DSM, even at a lower resolution of 80 m or 160 m, than using GLO-30 at 20 metres of resolution.

4. CONCLUSION

4.1 Better RTC results using VHR DEMs than MR DEMs

Massif de la Dôle, France – Area 1	La Réunion, France – Area 1
Massif de la Dôle, France – Area 2	La Réunion, France – Area 2
Massif de la Dôle, France – Area 3	La Réunion, France – Area 3
Notre-Dame-du-Pré, France – Area 1	La Becca, Trentino, Italy – Area 1
Notre-Dame-du-Pré, France – Area 2	La Becca, Trentino, Italy – Area 2

fig. 40 – RTC using MR and VHR DEMs at 20 metres of resolution – Overview of the study.

As seen in section 3, in all the cases, **using Very High Resolution DEMs (RGEALTI and ITA-TRE_DSM) for the RTC gives better results than using the Medium Resolution DEM (Copernicus DEM GLO-30)**. These results are summarized in fig. 40, in which one can see more homogeneous surfaces using the VHR DEMs than using the MR DEM.

4.2 VHR DEMs are still the best ones at lower resolutions

Massif de la Dôle, France – Area 1	La Réunion, France – Area 1
Massif de la Dôle, France – Area 2	La Réunion, France – Area 2
Massif de la Dôle, France – Area 3	La Réunion, France – Area 3
Notre-Dame-du-Pré, France – Area 1	La Becca, Trentino, Italy – Area 1
Notre-Dame-du-Pré, France – Area 2	La Becca, Trentino, Italy – Area 2

fig. 41 – RTC using MR and VHR DEMs at 20 metres of resolution – Overview of the study.

As seen in section 3, **using VHR DEMs (RGEALTI and ITA-TRE DSM) aggregated at 80 m to 160 m of resolution still give better RTC results than using the MR DEM (Copernicus DEM GLO-30) at 20 metres.** These results are summarized in fig. 41, in which one can see more homogeneous surfaces using the VHR DEMs than using the MR DEM.

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